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An Innovative Method of Infusing Global Competencies in Curriculum by Utilizing International Student Bodies

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1 INTRODUCTION

Rapidly changing global economy has transformed the way business operate and has changed the character of the engineering profession. Globalization of markets and advancement of information technology have provided engineering companies and alike an opportunity to produce differentiated products and services and reached every possible geographic location on the earth. More and more projects are now distributed across global sites and effective collaboration requires professionals who can work productively with colleagues who are very different from themselves. As a result many companies are now looking for engineers with global competency capable of providing engineering solutions not only in domestic market but beyond domestic boundaries [1]. Global competence is defined as a set of multidimensional capacities which enable individual to examine local, global and intercultural issues, understand and appreciate different perspectives and world views, interact successfully and respectfully with others, and take responsible action toward collective well-being [2]. Globally competent students can combine multi-disciplinary knowledge by asking the right questions, can analyse connected data and explain phenomena which create opportunities to take informed decisions. Globally competent students also recognize the perspectives and views different from themselves and are able to interact and communicate with people across cultures and regions in appropriate ways which foster collaboration and innovative problem solving. However, our college curricula have often failed to adequately preparing students with this very important global competency skill.

Academic, industry and government institutions have recognized the need of global competencies for engineering students. For example, Montgomery (2009) attributed improved student views in cross-cultural group work to internationalization efforts [3]. He noted that most of the project participants have pointed out that the year spent

abroad helped them develop ability to accept challenges and solve problems independently which may not be experienced in the U.S. Grandin (2006) discussed the value added to the engineering students through the experience of engineering work and study abroad, as well as on the lessons learned over the seventeen year history of the University of Rhode Island program [4]. The paper emphasized that to be competitive in global workplace engineers must be educated as global citizens, trained to work in global teams, and prepared to develop and manufacture for a global market. Without these skills, they will fail and their work will be handed off to peers from other parts of the world where such global preparation is already valued and broadly practiced. A series of studies focused on best practices for both scholars and practitioners of global engineering practices [5, 6, 7]. Being able to communicate and work effectively across cultures has been valued by potential employers; in fact, 78% of surveyed employers stressed the importance of all students gaining intercultural skills [8]. The U.S. National Academy of Engineering published two reports - both stress the impact of globalization on the practice of engineering and the need for U.S. engineers to focus on innovation and creative aspects of the profession to be globally competitive.

Various approaches are taken by universities to internationalize engineering education which include various types of study abroad, research abroad or internship programs or a combination of these, e.g. the GEARE at Purdue, the MISTI at MIT, or the IEP at URI. Parkinson (2007) has compiled a comprehensive overview of these different attempts to globalize engineering education via exchange programs, dual degree programs, international project work and internships [9]. The above mentioned programs are very effective to develop global competence for engineering students. However, several constraints such as desirability, affordability, language, safety etc. pose as major barriers for most students to participate in such programs. As a result, statistics show that only about 1.6% of American students studied abroad last year during their undergraduate programs [10].

International student groups bring significant cultural diversity on a university campus. In 2016/17, an estimated 1.07 million international students studied in US [10]. International students and associations promote awareness of cultural diversity and global understanding within the university and the broader community. Engaging local students with these diverse groups of international students through activities, group projects, and discussions can be an effective way of exposing students to learn cultural diversity, practices, ethics, and thereby preparing engineers for the global workforce.

2 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

2.1 Research Questions

This paper focuses on preparing engineers students as a global citizen and problem solver by systematically engaging them with the international student groups. The project has two research questions

1. Can international student groups and communities on the university campus help engineering students learn global skills through active and peer learning?
2. If yes, how effective is it? A comparative study will answer this question.

2.2 Planning For the Project

It requires some planning to systematically engage international students with local students. First a suitable course, ENTC 4600: Technical Practicum, was selected. This

is a senior level required capstone design course, which is offered every semester with enrollment of about 40 students each year. The course requires the student to synthesize and apply subject matter studies in previous required courses and apply them to a realistic problem solving effort. For example, in manufacturing, students will draw upon their knowledge of product design and manufacturing methods to solve a complex problem, commonly designing and developing a manufactured product. In a typical project students identify a product or service need in collaboration with the community or industry and then design and develop it from scratch. In the Fall of 2017, the project is modified as such that students looked at international markets mainly developing countries, identified an engineering and technology related problem (i.e. a product and service needs) with the collaboration of an international student group at X University, and then devised a solution (i.e. designed and developed a product or service) to meet the customers' needs.

During the summer of 2017, author as the instructor of the course made necessary changes in the course curriculum to add the international dimensions through research and development. Author identified textbook, case studies, journal articles, web contents, audio-visual contents, etc. and developed a modified course curriculum. Authors also recruited a group of international students from China and Nigeria to collaborate with students during the Fall semester. The international students were briefed about the goals, activities and expectations of the project. The international students were divided into two groups. The first international student group took part during idea generation and collaborated with the teams throughout the semester. The second group took part as a focus group to provide unbiased evaluation to the solutions.

2.3 Execution of the Project

Two weeks before the semester started students were introduced the new internationalization infused course curriculum. Students were encouraged to research global markets and generate ideas of creative products and services for their country of interest. At the end of first week of class, students were formally introduced to the international student group. After a short introduction, the author explained the goals and objectives of the project, collaboration process and expectations from both local and international student groups. Four project requirements were identified. These four project requirements were: 1) The solution (the product) meets the requirements of the clients' needs in the country of interest, 2) Regional design standards, specifications, practices as well as cultural, economical and social factors are considered appropriately in the design and development of the solution, 3) The solution is sustainable, and 4) The solution has potentials for future enhancements.

A total of 4 groups were formed. For the comparative study, one group was used as a control who had to work on an international project without any engagement with the international students. Quickly students (local and international) started to brainstorm and they spent two sessions discussing project ideas and at the end of second sessions four engineering problem solving projects were identified focusing on Asian nation of China and African nation of Nigeria. Students then put their ideas into design and developed a prototype to meet the customer/community needs making sure that the solution is culturally, socially and environmentally justified. As the students dive into the projects, author taught concepts of engineering problem solving from global perspective using texts, reports, journal articles, case studies, audio, video, etc. Four guest speakers were invited who talked about design and development, international business environment, business plan, manufacturing, testing, and specifications appropriate global communities throughout the semester. At the end of semester

students presented their product and services, and the second international student group evaluated them. Students prepared a report with detail design, manufacturing processes and specifications.

3 ASSESSMENT OF STUDENT LEARNING OUTCOMES

The course has five learning outcomes which are aligned with ABET student outcomes a to h. Two additional learning outcomes were added focusing on global perspectives of engineering problems and solution. These are:

1. Understanding of International Business Environment

The current learning outcome for the course is somewhat “Think Local, Act Local”. Students identify an engineering problem in the community or in industry and then develop a product or service to fit local customers, regulations, and market requirements. The proposed learning outcomes was to broaden it to “Think Global, Act Global”. Students are expected to learn about global business dynamics, economic interdependence, environmental risks, conflicts, manufacturing principles, regulations, logistics, etc. which will enhance students understanding about multinational businesses and global engineering problems, and needs for solutions.

2. Ability to Incorporate Cross Cultural Elements to Engineering Problems and Solutions

Differing population sizes, income levels, demographic, political and cultural factors give rise to considerable differences in market size. Buyer tastes for a particular product or service sometimes differ substantially from country to country. Sometimes, product designs suitable in one country are inappropriate in another because of differing local standards – for example, in USA electrical devices run on 110 volt systems, but in south East Asian countries the standard is a 240 volt, necessitating the use of different electrical design and components. Students have to decide whether and how much to customize their products or services to match the tastes and preferences of local buyers of a geographic location. Students are expected to learn about all these cultural, political and economic forces that drive and are driven by technology and how to factor in those in product design and development. Students also need to consider critical global environmental issues and make sure that sustainable solutions are considered and implemented in their products or service development.

Two summative assessments were utilized in the course – final project judge by a faculty panel and peer evaluation by both local and international students.

3.1 Students’ Performance

The anticipated outcomes of the students’ learning were assessed through evaluation of a series of student presentations and report writings. Students prepared a total of 5 presentations, four item based reports and a final report – each chronologically depicts search for an engineering problem in their country of interest, understanding of various dimensions of international arena, conceptual design focusing on local preferences, a business plan, prototype design, manufacturing process and the final product development. A pre and a post survey were conducted to assess effectiveness of learning outcomes.

The pre survey assessed students’ initial understanding of global citizenship, their knowledge and preparation, and willingness to engage in local, global, and intercultural problem solving. Students were asked Yes/No questions and/or rate

statements based on 5 point Likert scale: 1- strongly disagree, 2 – disagree, 3 – neither agree nor disagree, 4 – agree and 5- strongly agree. Table 1 shows students' responses and rating percentage in key items of the pre survey. As shown in Table 1, most students had no international experience (82%) and unfamiliar with engineering and technology related standards and specifications outside USA (80%). However, about 82% students responded that they understand interplay among regional cultures, socio- economical and political influences in engineering problems and development of solutions.

Table 1. Pre Survey Responses

Question or Statements	Yes	No	Likert Scale Rating				
			1	2	3	4	5
Do you have an international education experience such as study abroad?	18%	82%					
I can communicate effectively at least one foreign language	18%	82%					
I am familiar with SI Units for problem solving	100%						
I am familiar with engineering and technology related standards and specifications outside USA	20%	80%					
U.N. Millennium Development Goals, which USA supports, also reflect the need for a Global Education Perspective to achieve success.					10%	27%	63%
I see the relevance of international issues such as cultural, socio-economical, political etc. in engineering problems and solutions			9%	9%		36%	46%
I believe that in future, I will need to work in environment where the communication with individuals with different background, knowledge and/or language will be necessary				18%		18%	64%
I value diversity and multi-perspective analysis of an issue			9%		27%		64%
I believe understanding sustainability is essential to join the international discourse and work cooperatively in the closely interconnected world of the new millennium			9%	10%		36%	45%
I am preparing myself to be a global citizen			10%	10%	20%	40%	20%

Significant number of students value diversity and believe that in future they will work in diverse environments. More than 80% students emphasize the importance of sustainable solutions and 60% students responded that they are preparing themselves to be global citizen.

A post-survey was conducted to assess students' global learning experience and effectiveness of course program. A similar format as in pre survey was used in developing the survey. Table 2 summarizes students' responses and rating percentage in key items of the post survey. As shown in Table 2, engaging international students in identifying engineering and technology related problems and solutions was a huge success. All students agreed that the course project increased their knowledge and skills to solve engineering problems in global settings. The students utilized their knowledge of mathematics, science, and tools and techniques learned in other technology courses and significantly challenged their critical thinking skills. About 92% students responded that the project increased their interest about different cultures and multi-perspective analysis, and 72% students, up 52% from pre-

survey, said that the project was helpful understanding engineering and technology related practices, standards, specifications, safety outside USA. Since sustainability was a project requirement, at least 65% reported that the course materials and the project expanded students' knowledge about sustainability by balancing environmental protection, social responsibility and economic growth.

Table 2. Post Survey Responses

Question or Statements	Yes	No	Likert Scale Rating				
			1	2	3	4	5
The project increased my knowledge and skills to solve engineering problems in global settings	91%	9%					
Did the project challenge you to use critical thinking skills?	100						
The project prepares me to apply the knowledge of mathematics, science and engineering to design systems, components or processes	100						
The project prepares me to conduct tests and measurements, and interpret experimental results	92%	8%					
Was this experience helpful understanding engineering and technology related practices, standards, specifications, safety outside USA?	72%	28%					
Does this project increase you interest about different cultures, practices, diversity, multi-perspective analysis?	92%	8%					
The project enhances my teamwork and leadership skills						10%	90%
The project improves time, cost, quality and communication management skills						12%	88%
The course materials and the project expand my knowledge about sustainability by balancing environmental protection, social responsibility and economic growth at home and abroad				14%	21%	57%	8%

3.2 Comparison with the control group

A comparative study was conducted to learn any differential experience between the students who worked with the international students versus the control group (who didn't work with the international students). Fig. 1 shows side by side comparison of the five post survey measures. It was found that the differences in students' experience was statistically insignificant at $\alpha = 5\%$ significance level. However, it is evident that in each measure students who engaged with international students had better learning experiences than those who have not. Informal discussion revealed that students in the control group struggled to find a suitable project for their country of interest. They had to "guess" a lot during product design and development because specific information was unavailable. Students who worked with the international students appreciate the interaction and collaboration with international students which helped them to learn tacit and socially complex knowledge such as cultural aspects, social norms, standards, local practices which could be unreachable without such interactions.

Fig.1. Comparative assessment of students' learning between team with and without international student engagement

4 CONCLUSIONS

If our students are expected to understand and resolve global challenges and compete in global economy, it becomes crucial for educators to address and cultivate student global competence. Global competency is essential for engineers from any country which now competes in an international market for engineering know-how. Engineering students who have international study experience are more likely to be hired and prepared for the global market place. However, very few American engineering students have any international experience. A vast majority of students have little to no exposure to investigate engineering problems and solutions under global lens. This paper presents an alternative yet effective method of teaching students global competency. This method involves systematically engaging students with the international student groups and communities through group activities, team project, discussion and other activities. Based on the data presented, the proposed course modifications greatly enhance students' understanding about global engineering problems, how to develop socially justified sustainable solutions and be a global citizen. The course project significantly challenge students' critical thinking skills and help them understanding engineering and technology related practices, standards, specifications, safety outside USA. This will ultimately increase students' employability and advance their career in global economy.

5 LIMITATION OF THE STUDY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The major limitation of the paper is that inferences are made based on limited data. More data collection and focused analysis are necessary to further validate the premise. One key challenge was coordination between American and international students and keeping both groups focused. This author recommends extensive planning, focused lecturing and briefing on global skills, developing extensive guidelines for collaboration, and stipends for international students for better results.

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